

The Impact Of Gender Conflict On National Development In Nigeria

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Abstract

Women throughout world history are struggling to elevate their socio-economic and political status to those of men who occupy positions of power, wealth and status. This has created atmosphere of tension and gender conflict affecting national development negatively. Gender conflict has caused development setbacks as most women are being denied access to resources accessed by men. In Nigeria society gender conflict ensues as women attempt to foster equality with men to also enjoy all the rights and privileges. From the foregoing, the study examined the causes of gender conflict and ascertains its impact on national development in Nigeria. Secondary methods of data collection were employed, sourced from textbooks, journals, internet, among others, and analyzed historically. The paper employed Feminist and Social Class theories as its theoretical framework. The findings of the paper include inter alia: That gender conflict has taken prominent stage as women have continuously struggle to be equal with male in all areas of human endeavours, men also have continued to subject women under control by paying no attention to their rights and responsibilities. The study concluded that for Nigeria to attain its full potentials; gender equality must be given adequate attention to tap the talents of women to promote national development. The paper recommended that the government should advocate promulgate policies and laws that empower women, and change cultural attitudes restricting gender equity.

Keywords: Conflict, Development, Equality, Gender, Inequality, National

INTRODUCTION

Gender conflict occurs out of societal struggles and tensions arising from the disparities between men and women, both in the family unit and the public sectors. This is because many Nigerian societies have traditional beliefs and practices that placed women in disadvantage position. An attempt to extricate themselves from the domination of men breeds conflict. Gender conflict has taken the front burner as women try to disentangle themselves from societal barriers, such as areas of employment, disproportionate pay, and inadequate access to resources among others. From observation, in the Northern parts of Nigeria, male education is sometimes prioritized by cultural attitudes over female education, thus results in lower educational attainment for women and girls. Women are underrepresented which limits their authority on policies affecting their welfare and well-being. Although there are laws, efforts and interventional initiatives aimed at promoting gender equality, but their enforcement is often weak. The above underlining issues underscore the conflicts which hinder Nigeria's overall development.

Gender conflict has notably hindered national development in social, economic, political, and human capital aspects in Nigeria. This is imperative as women and girls are daily facing general obstacles due to gender discrimination and inequality leading to low productivity and female illiteracy rates. In parts of northern Nigeria, early marriage and gender norms keep girls out of school. This contributes to a less educated workforce, halting national improvement and human capital development. In reality, gender conflict manifests across south and north divides of Nigeria, particularly in the north where girls are often married as early as 12–15 years old [1]. The incidences of Boko Haram have targeted women, abducted Chibok school girls, forced marriages leading to sexual slavery. Nigeria women are vastly relegated in decision-making, planning, design and implementation of development programmes which not only affect them but also national development. This neglect has reduced their relevance in their political and socio-economic status leading to poverty [1].

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Significance of the study

The study is embarked on to uncover the causes of gender conflict and its effect on national development as well as proffering ways gender conflict can be reduced to the lowest ebbs. The findings of the paper will encourage and guide policymakers, activists, and

researchers on ways to address gender conflict and promote sustainable development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gender Inequality

Gender inequality is a human rights issue and it is considered as a requirement for sustainable development [2]. Gender equality in a country is an essential factor for sustainable security and stability [3]. This means the idea of excluding women from actively participating in society can increase the risk of disequilibrium and instability in a system. Gender equality is also an important element in economic development and a critical predictor of stability and security, which can inform and improve work on conflict prevention. According to Aisedion (4) gender includes the way in which societies differentiate appropriate behaviour and access to power for women and men. It implies that gender is related to the behaviours, roles, activities, attributes and opportunities that any society considers suitable for women and girls, men and boys. Equality of gender connotes both women and men should enjoy equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities [5]. Equality therefore, further means that rights and privileges of an individual should not be decided base on male and female. The interests, needs and priorities of both women and men should be taken into consideration for fair distribution of resources [6]. In most societies some are better off than others where there are discriminations and inequalities between women and men in social and political responsibilities, cultural and religious activities allowed, access to public offices and control over resources, as well as decision-making opportunities.

Gender inequality is associated with barriers affecting female in terms of opportunities, economic and social activities. The presence of barriers gives certain people advantage and access to a better chance of societal resources, [7]; [8]; [9]. For equitable development Nigeria needs to treat gender inequality issue with strong commitment and sincerity. According to Ndubuisi (10), the imbalance in gender allocation of resources in society and sectors of the economy is still widened in spite of several strategies adopted by United Nations, the government of nations and various private to reduce gender inequality to the bare minimum. In light of the gender conflict, this study seeks to critically evaluate its causes, interventions made by government and Non-governmental Organizations and its impact on national development in Nigeria. According to Olonade (11), gender is a social construct and a product of socialization where societal expectations are learnt as either males or females. It is essential to note that gender determined what is valued and allowed in a man or a woman in a particular situation. To further buttress, this is why an

individual's sex, determines society's socialization. The concept of gender connotes the culturally and socially constructed roles with both men and women in society [12]. Gender as a social construct is learned, and gender role and judgment are also learned through socialization that existed before they were born. Several social attributes and privileges connected with being male and female are also issues relating to gender [11].

Gender Conflict

According to Byrne (13), gender conflict refers to conflicting interests and inequalities between men and women over resources and power between male and female. Majority of society's males controls and oppresses females by appropriating the position of leadership and such appropriation has led to unequal treatment and conflict. Many communities adhere to patriarchal norms that limit women's roles to domestic responsibilities. This affects women's access to education, healthcare, and employment, contributing to gender inequality and conflict.

Development

According to Amunnadi (14), development relates to the reduction of poverty, inequality, hunger, unemployment, diseases, among others. This implies that development is not only the availability of infrastructure but the provision of adequate food, employment, affordable education and equality of men and women access to public resources. This implies that development is essential for a country to provide qualitative life for her citizenry. Development is an improvement in the conditions of human existence in all ramifications [15]. This means development is sure when there is improvement in the living condition as well as material well-being of all citizens, and to the degree of reducing poverty and inequality to the barest minimum. Naomi (16), believes that development involves equitable distribution, provision of health care, education, housing and other essential services all with a view to improving the individual and collective quality of life. So development includes societal improvement in the well-being of people in society. Development involves both socio-economic and political issues and pervades all aspects of societal life [17].

National Development

National development refers to the general improvement or common advancement in the political, religious, healthcare, education, infrastructure, and economic opportunities for a better quality of life for all citizens in respective of their status [6]. When people are emancipated from discrimination, poverty, unemployment, hunger, environmental degradation, illiteracy, diseases amongst others, then development becomes national. Rodney cited in Aisedion (18),

captured development as the capability for self-supporting growth with an increased ability to produce. From this definition, human beings' contributions are required to lift a nation from underdevelopment. From Asen (19), development is the process of mobilizing all the available human and material resources of a society to achieve quality of living standard. This suggests that development include basic human needs for a rewarding life to be attained. Seers cited in Aisedion (18), see development in terms of a reduction in poverty, unemployment and inequality. From the foregoing to talk of national development is to talk about collective improvement in the socio-economic and political life of the people to reduce poverty, inequality and unemployment that have caused gender conflict in society. Ogbenika (20), sees national development as sustainable growth and holistic development of a nation and its citizens. This involves the development of the human person, is necessary to improve his material conditions of living through the use of resources available to him. According to Okoli, etal (21), national development should be human-oriented and not physical infrastructure. They add that, national development refers to unity, education, economic well-being and mass participation in government. So the core elements of democracy include participation by the majority and representation. According to Okeke and Ifeagwazi (22), refers to national development as the well-being of a majority of the citizens of a state in material terms. Therefore, when talking about national development a country must engage the majority of its people to share from the public goods. According to Idike (23), national development is seeing as ability to eliminate inequality levels as well as the assuring the people the security of their lives and property. National development is therefore predicated upon the holistic development of the human resources in a nation expressed in an improved standard of living, and the political, socio-economic, and educational growth that underpins the sustainability of the nation.

Gender and National Development

Gender issues are worrisome as women are discriminated against in matters of economy, policymaking, education and opportunity in general. Women are human beings are they need full support and the opportunity to display their talents and expertise in diverse sectors. From all indications women are not supported by men. For instance, in politics and public life participation of women is very low in the Northern region. However, women in Southern Nigeria were recognized and granted the right to vote in 1959. It was after twenty years 1979 Northern Nigerian women were allowed to vote [24]. NBS cited in Eke (25), the number of seats held by women in the House of Representatives and the Senate since 1999 has shown that women have been under-represented in the National Assembly where they

occupy only 6.4% of seats held by women in the Nigerian Senate and House of Representatives for the 2007 and 2011 general elections. Female political representation was negligible in 2015 and 2019 elections considering the population they constitute, with 2,970 women on the electoral ballot, representing only 11.36 percent of elected candidates. Furthermore, PLAC cited in Eke (25) there were 7 Female Senators in the Senate in 2015 and 2019 elections, while in the House of Representatives in 2015 women were 22 (6.8%) out of 360 members and declined to a mere 11 in 2019 (3.05%). The 8th National Assembly consisted of only 7 females out of 109 senate seats available, 22 females out of the 360 House of representatives seats available and also in the 9th National Assembly, there were only 7 females out of 109 Senators, 11 females out of the 360 House of Representative Members. Raji (26) for the 10th Assembly, women got two seats in the Senate and 13 seats in the House of Representatives which indicates a decline in female participation.

Theoretical Framework

Analyzing the impact of gender conflict on national development in this study involves two theoretical frameworks; Feminist and Social Conflict theories. Feminist theory which according to Tucker, cited in Aisedion (27) begins with the works of Mary Wollstonecraft (1759–1797), one of the first feminist writers in the liberal tradition. Feminist political theory is a movement for the liberation of women and collective struggle for equality. This movement consisted women's liberation groups, advocacy, protests and consciousness-raising, sought to free women from male supremacy and oppression. In these movements, gender was social expression of male as a master and superior being and female as a slavish being, with unequal pay, unequal status, recipient of domestic violence and sexual violence. Gender inequality is expressed as masculine values with domineering authority over a female who have no say and opportunity to advance her course and talent.

Social conflict according to Karl Marx 1848 who is the primary advocate sees it as the struggle for power and opportunity in society. It occurs when there is opposing interest in social interaction, resource allocation, responsibilities and the prevention of other opponents' from attaining their own ambition [28]. It is a social relationship in which action is intentionally oriented to carry out the actor's own will despite the resistance of others Social conflicts arise from competition over resources and power, suggesting that inequalities can lead to tensions and conflict. It involves opposing interests, goals, or values between individuals or groups, leading to tension, disagreement, or antagonism. This struggle can manifest in various forms, from interpersonal disputes to large-scale social movements. These theories help to explain the

dynamics of gender conflict and their effects on national development. Feminist theory seeks to explain the need for gender equity and seeks to address systemic conflict which is inequality. Applying Feminist and Social Conflict theories to analyze gender conflict unveil the inequalities in distribution of resources, access to education, and decision-making being dominated by men and the struggle by women to free themselves from the second fiddle results in conflict. The very discrepancies in gender roles and expectations can create social tensions that impede developmental efforts of any country. Also neglecting gender-specific needs can lead to conflict, ultimately hindering national growth as gender conflict limits women's and marginalized groups' talents, capabilities, and impacting overall national development. As was noted above, women political participation in Nigeria is on the low ebb as they are discriminated against and given little or no opportunity to participate in politics. Anyalebechi (29), points out inequality and gap in women participation in politics, such as culture and norms favouring the male; education level of women also contribute to the low participation; and as such relegated to domestic work. The political factor and the rule of law are not favorable to women in politics. This framework highlights the subjugation of women and the challenges they encounter in a patriarchal society that position men as dominant in political spaces, ultimately placing women at a disadvantage and conflict in society.

ANALYSIS

Causes of Gender Conflict in Nigeria

Causes of gender conflict in Nigeria include: gender inequality which refers to unequal treatment of individuals wholly or partly due to their gender or sex. It arises from differences in socially constructed gender roles. Gender inequality in Nigeria is influenced by different cultures and beliefs. In most parts of Nigeria, women are considered subordinate to their male counterparts, especially in Northern Nigeria [30]. It is generally believed that women are best suited as home keepers, as such should not be heard and entrusted with positions of authority [31]

Cultural norms and tradition affect women and girls in most African societies. Nigeria is often confronted with various forms of harmful traditional practices from female genital mutilation, child marriage. This denies girls to educational opportunities, leading to a situation of less gender equality and conflict. Education increases people's opportunities to become economically active and autonomous decision makers, but women are often restricted in these capacities by norms and institutions. Early marriage has serious health and social implications for young brides, for the wellbeing of the family, poses many dangers to young girls' health. It also results in marital instability,

psychological trauma and limited alternatives, which often end in poor employment and even exposure to HIV/AIDS. Invariably, the lack of other opportunities and the powerlessness that accompanies early marriage perpetuate the gender roles of girls and women and reinforce cultural traditions that support early marriage as a desirable practice [32].

According to World Bank report (33), across the world, women earn less money than men due to factors like differences in education, pay discrimination and motherhood. This implies that economic factors drive gender conflict by creating gender pay gap, perpetuating unequal access to resources and hindering women's economic resources. This often leads to social tensions, poverty and gender based violence.

The legal institutionalization of discrimination, limits women leading to gender conflict particularly in areas like, marriage, inheritance and divorce. Laws affecting marriage, divorce, and inheritance give women unequal rights compared to men. Laws that deny women the right to acquire and manage assets, or restrict their ability to participate in the labor force, create economic disparities that fuel conflict [34].

Violence against women is a threat to women's lives; because it puts their psychological and physical health at risk. It is a threat to the well-being of their relations and children around them. The United Nations defines violence against women as act of gender-based violence that results in physical, sexual, or mental harm, including arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life [35].

Religion controls the social landscape of social, economic maintaining gender inequality and conflict in society. Religion dictates the status of women and has continually been a foundation upon which gender conflict rests on. It is assumed that gender roles are constructed through culture, religion and upbringing [36].

One of the causes of gender conflict is educational inequality. This is by creating power imbalances, hindering economic opportunities, and reinforcement of restrictive traditional gender roles and female underrepresentation across many sectors [37]. Many people still think that it is more relevant for a boy to go to school than a girl and that they are likely to be involved in child bearing and domestic work than boys.

The Impact of Gender Conflict on National Development in Nigeria

Gender conflict has extensively hindered national development in Nigeria by creating political, social and economic inequalities among the people. The demonstration of inequality include inter alia: unequal

access to healthcare and education, restricted representation in political and decision-making processes, poor economic opportunities, among others. Gender conflicts lead to disparities in access to resources and economic opportunities and increase in poverty [38]. It hinders national development by exacerbating poverty, limiting opportunities for growth. It creates a gap where the poor struggle to improve their socio-economic status and undermine efforts to achieve sustainable development. The United Nations Development program (39), lamented that a one per cent increase in gender inequality reduces a country's development index. This clearly demonstrates that not including adequate number of women in the developmental effort of any society is detrimental to the realization of developmental goals of that society.

Gender-based violence and discrimination can undermine social stability and cohesion within communities. This conflict has led to a breakdown of families and community structures. Gender conflict, stemming from unequal power dynamics and harmful gender norms, significantly undermines social stability and cohesion within communities by creating divisions, fostering violence, and hindering development. This conflict can manifest as violence against women, exclusion from decision-making and unequal access to resources, all of which contribute to social fragmentation [40]. Gender inequality restricts women's access to education, employment, and resources, hindering their economic potential and the overall development of the community. Violence and conflict erode trust and social networks, weakening the social capital necessary for community development and resilience. When women are excluded from decision-making processes, it can lead to policies and programs that do not adequately address the needs of all community members, hindering development efforts [41].

Gender conflicts often result in underrepresentation of women in political processes. This limits the diverse perspectives needed for comprehensive national development policies. Gender conflicts often contribute to the underrepresentation of women in political processes. These conflicts stem from various factors, including societal norms, cultural biases, and political structures that favor male leadership, hindering women's participation. The participation of women in both elective and appointive positions in Nigeria remains notably low, despite global and national efforts to promote gender inclusion. The Fourth World Conference on Women, held in Beijing, advocated for a minimum of 35% representation of women in political and leadership roles, a benchmark echoed by Nigeria's National Gender Policy (NGP). However, female representation continues to fall short of this target, persisting as a historical challenge from pre-

colonial times to the present [42]. The underrepresentation of women in elective and appointive positions in Nigeria is an exceptional issue of worrisome proportion. The exclusion of women from majority political commitment undermines 25%, average of Global women's political participation, making Nigeria 7% behind female representation. The underrepresentation of Nigerian women in politics, question the credibility of Nigeria's democratic system since 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, and 2023 elections [42].

Gender conflict affects health outcomes adversely, particularly in issues related to access to reproductive health services hinder overall public health improvements. Gender conflict, particularly gender inequality impact maternal mortality and has negative impacts on health, especially for women. These impacts stem from various factors, including reduced access to healthcare, increased exposure to violence and harmful practices. The fact that women are excluded from schooling, or from participation in public life, affects their knowledge about health problems and how to prevent and treat them [43].

Gender conflicts have enormously hindered efforts to achieve equality and development. Societal norms often restrict women's roles in leadership and decision-making. Traditional gender roles and expectations can indeed perpetuate gender conflicts and hinder efforts to achieve equality. By limiting individuals based on their gender, these roles can create barriers to opportunities, reinforce stereotypes, and lead to social hierarchies where one gender is dominant over another. This, in turn, can manifest as discrimination, violence, and a lack of representation in various aspects of life, ultimately impeding progress towards a more equitable society. Deep-rooted social and cultural norms cause and often perpetuate gender inequalities. For example, traditional beliefs about gender roles often limit economic opportunities for women, leading to disparities in access to education, employment, and leadership positions [44].

Gender conflict has led to unequal educational opportunities for girls, impacting literacy rates and educational attainment. This adds to poverty and limits national progress and development. Gender-based conflict, including harmful traditional practices, has largely restricted girls' access to education and negatively impact their literacy rates and educational attainment. These limitations stems from factors like forced early marriage, societal expectations that prioritize boys' education, and unsafe school environments [45].

Gender conflicts direct resource allocation only towards male-dominated sectors, leaving women's

needs unaddressed. This affects overall economic productivity and social welfare. This disparity stems from power imbalances and unequal access to resources and opportunities. Gender-based employment segregation carries important costs for the economy. As gender gaps in human capital are reduced (even reversed) across the globe, the higher concentration of women in low productivity jobs or jobs with fewer hours is an increasingly important form of labor misallocation [46].

Excluding women from the workforce significantly diminishes the available talents, hindering national development. This exclusion limits the potential contributions of women to various sectors, impacting economic growth, innovation, and overall societal progress. A diverse workforce, including women, is crucial for a nation's development. Gender inequality reduces living quality and leads to decreased productivity, which impedes economic efficiency and growth [47]. People are the valuable resources of a country and the loss of potential talent in strategic positions and divisions is devastation for the country, especially when it affects gender issues.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Gender conflict arises as a result of discrimination of women in cultural, political, social, and economic activities in society. This discrimination has undermined societal stability and cohesion thereby affecting national development. This is because national development entails even improvement in the lives of everybody in society without discrimination. Any attempt to improve a country with an act of discrimination against the female gender only accounts for a rapid setback and counter-productivity of that country. Addressing gender conflict is therefore crucial for building peaceful, stable, and prosperous country as stated below:

1. Women should be allowed to participate fully with men in the planning and execution of policies in government geared towards sustainable development. This is because women participation in the decision making process and access to power is crucial and fundamental to the achievement of equality, development and peace.
2. Women should be given unreserved rights to vote and be voted for key political offices. Development is truly national when women are empowered to act freely, exercise their rights, and fulfill their potentials as full and equal members of society.
3. There should be political leadership training for women, gender quotas, and reforms to reduce bias and to instill confidence in women.
4. Women should be exposed to their fundamental human rights. This would help in eliminating destructive and subjugating cultural

practices like gender-based violence, female genital mutilation, and other obnoxious and dehumanizing practices like sexual abuse suffered by women and even young girls in society

5. Government should make policies that will empower girls and women, and also to change cultural attitudes limiting gender equity.

REFERENCES

1. Oluwatusin, A.O. The Place of Women In Modern Nigeria's Political and Economic Development. In Ola, R.F.(ed.), *Whiter Nigeria?* (2020).
2. Bouta, Y., Frerks, G & Bannon, I. Gender, Conflict, and Development,. The World Bank (2005) [Accessed 27-7-2025, 3:45 am] https://landwise-production.s3.amazonaws.com/2022/03/Bouta_Gender-Conflict-and-Development_2005.pdf
3. Crespo-Sancho, C. Can gender equality prevent violent conflict? Development for Peace (2018). [Accessed 30-07-2025, 8:24pm] <https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/dev4peace/can-gender-equality-prevent-violent-conflict>
4. Aisedion, R. The policy of gender equality and its prospects on European Union. *Zamfara Journal of Politics and Development* | Vol. 3 No. 3 | December (2022). [Accessed 18-07-2025,5:45pm]<file:///C:/Users/USERS%20PC/Desktop/GENDER%20EQUAKITY%20BY%20RUFUS.pdf>
5. United Nations. Gender equality and women's empowerment, 2021, United Nations Sustainable Development website:[Accessed 11-8-2025, 6:54pm] Available online:<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/genderequality>
6. Aisedion, R. & Omoregie, E. The Security Implications of Human Trafficking for National Development: the Nigeria Experience. *International Journal of Management, Social Sciences, Peace and Conflict Studies (IJMSSPCS)*, Vol.4 No.1, 211 - 221; (2021). [Accessed14-7-2025, 5:45pm]. Available online:https://www.academia.edu/97739265/The_Security_Implications_of_Human_Trafficking_for_National_Development_The_Nigeria_Experience#loswp-work-container
7. Kleven, H.& Landais, C. (2017), "*Gender inequality and economic development: fertility, education and norms*", *Economica*, Vol. 84 No. 334, pp. 180-209.
8. Matthew, O., Adeniji, A., Osabohien, R., Olawande, T. and Atolagbe, T. (2020), "*Gender inequality, maternal mortality and inclusive growth in Nigeria*", *Social Indicators Research*, Vol. 147 No. 3, p p. 763-780.
9. Ndubuisi, P. Analysis of the impact of external debt on economic growth in an Emerging Economy: evidence from Nigeria", *African Research Review*, Vol. 11 No. 4, pp. 156-173. (2017),
10. Olonade, O.Y, Oyibode, B.O. Bashiru Idowu, B. O. George, T.O. Iwelumor, O.S. Ozoya, M A, M atthew E Egharevba , M.E. & Adetunde, C.O. Understanding Gender Issues in Nigeria: The Imperative for Sustainable Development. *Heliyon* 18;7(7) (2021). [Accessed 30-07-2025, 4:67 pm doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07622
11. Akinbi, J.O.& Akinbi, Y.A. Gender disparity in enrolment into basic formal education in Nigeria: implications for national development, *African Research Review*, Vol. 9 No. 3, pp. 11-23. (2015).
12. Byrne, B. *Towards a Gendered Understanding of Conflict* (1996) [Accessed 13-8-2025, 9:34pm] <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1759-5436.1996.mp27003004.x>
13. Amunnadi, C. A. Religion, peace, and national development: A reflection. His Glory Publishers. (2016)
14. Gboyega A Democracy and Development: The Imperative of Local Governance. An Inaugural Lecture, University of Ibadan, pp 6- 7 (2003).
15. Naomi O. Towards an Integrated View of Human Rights. *Hunger Teach Net*, 6(3): 6-7. (1995).
16. Lawal, T. & Oluwatoyin, A. National development in Nigeria: Issues, challenges and prospects. *African Journal of Political Science* ISSN 3461-2165 Vol. 11 (4), 001-005, (2017).[Accessed 12-7-2025, 7:45pm] Available online at www.international scholarsjournals.org © International Scholars Journals
17. Aisedion, R. Road Traffic Accident and its Implication for National Development In Nigeria: A Comparative Regional Analysis. A PhD Thesis Submitted to Postgraduate School, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna Nigeria. (2016).
18. Asen, R. Empowering the Adolescent Girl for Self and National Development Through the Theater for Development . *Multidisciplinary Journal of Research DevelopmentNards* (12)2, (2009)
19. Ogbenika, G. E. Gender Discourse and National Development in Nigeria. *Gora: Journal of Philosophical & Theological Studies* (2022). [Accessed10-7-2025, 4:36pm], [file:///C:/Users/USERS%20PC/Desktop/3092-Article%20Text-10076-1-10-20221212%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/USERS%20PC/Desktop/3092-Article%20Text-10076-1-10-20221212%20(1).pdf)
20. Okoli, J.O., Dialoke, I., Ekene, C., & Edwin, E. The tripod of women's role in national development in *International Journal of Innovative Psychology & Social Development* 7(2), 132-143. (2019).
21. Okeke, R. C., & Ifeagwazi, P. A. Public policy and national development in Nigeria: A focus on admission policies in tertiary education [Paper presentation] at the Eighth International Conference of the Society for Research and Academic Excellence, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, (2018). [Accessed 10-7-2025, 5:23am]. https://academicexcellencesociety.com/conference_proceedings_and_abstracts.htm.

22. Idike, A.N., Okeke, R.C. & Ugodulunwa, C.A. Gender, Democracy, and National Development in Nigeria .(2020) [Accessed 16-8-2025, 3:54pm. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020922836>
23. Aina., O I. Two Halves make one whole-Gender at the crossroad of national development. Inaugural Lecture delivered at Obafemi Awolowo University on 25th September, (2012)
24. Omoluabi, E & Aina, O. Gender in Nigeria's Development Discourse: Relevance of Gender Statistics in African Population Studies 27(2), 372-385. (2014)
25. Eke, B. O. Women's Representation in Nigeria's National Assembly: An Assessment of their Contributions to Legislative Activities of the 8th and 9th Assemblies. National Institute for Legislative and Democratic Studies. (2022). [Accessed 16-8-2025, 8:52pm]. Available online: <https://ir.nilds.gov.ng/handle/123456789/889?show=full>
26. Raji, M. 2023. Elections: Women get 15 out of 423 Senate, Reps seats. *vanguard* (2023).[Accessed 16-8-2025, 6:54pm] Available online: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2023/03/2023-elections-women-get-15-out-of-423-senate-reps-seats/>
27. Aisedion, R. Inclusiveness of Women with Disabilities in Politics and Governance in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects. In Oviasuyi, P.O., Ofanson, E. J., Osumah, O. & Okorodudu, E.(eds). *Issues in Humanities, Politics, Management and Development in Nigeria: A Festschrift for Friday Ebose Iyoha* Department of Public Administration Ambrose Alli University (ND)
28. Pruitt, D. G. & Kim, S. H. (Eds.), *Social Conflict, Escalation and Settlement in McGraw Hill Higher Education*, 35,(2004).
29. Anyalebechi, L. The issue of gender inequality in Nigeria", *Journal of Policy and Development Studies*, Vol. 289 No. 3519, pp. 1-9. (2016)
30. Abegunde, B. Gender Inequality: Nigerian and International Perspectives. *British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*. 17: 168. (2014). ISSN 2046-9578.
31. Einwechter, W. *Keepers at Home*. Darash Press. (ND)
32. Abimbola, O. H., Iruonagbe T. C., Dikko, B. O., Ojo, S. O. & Fasoranti, T.V. Gender Discrimination and Harmful Traditional Practices: A Focus on Nigeria. *F U O Y E Journal of Criminology and Security Studies (IJCSS)* Vol-3, Issue-2, June (2024)[Accessed 20-8-2025, 8:45pm]. Available online: [file:///C:/Users/USERS%20PC/Downloads/8%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/USERS%20PC/Downloads/8%20(1).pdf)
33. World Bank report. 13 Causes of Gender Inequality. *Human Right* (2022). [Accessed 23-8-2025, 7:45pm]. Available online: <https://www.humanrightscareers.com/issues/causes-gender-inequality/>
34. Osakwe, S. & Phung, N. Gender inequality and Ineffective Legal Frameworks in Nigeria and Vietnam. *Global Dev.*(2023). [Accessed 19-8-2025, 3:42pm] Available online: <https://globaldev.blog/gender-inequality-and-ineffective-legal-frameworks-in-nigeria-and-vietnam/>
35. World Health Organization. Violence against Women.(2024). [20-8-2025, 7:56pm]. Available online: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/violence-against-women>
36. Etim-James, G. The influence of culture and religion on gender inequality and its implications on women empowerment. *Wukari International Studies Journal*, Vol. 8 (5), (2024)[Accessed 13-8-2025, 9:45] Available online: <file:///C:/Users/USERS%20PC/Downloads/14.pdf>
37. GEM Report . Five steps to stamp out gender inequality in education. *World-education* (2022). [Accessed 22-8-2025, 7:52]. Available online: <https://world-education-blog.org/2019/07/05/five-steps-to-stamp-out-gender-inequality-in-education/>
38. Oxfam. *A tale of two continents: Fighting inequality in Africa*. Oxford, (2019).
39. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2016). *African Human Development Report 2016*. Accessed on the 21st of April 2022: <http://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/librarypage/hdr/2016-africahuman-development-report.html>
40. Roebig, T.D. *How Gender Discrimination Affects Women in the Workplace*, (ND) <http://www.florinroebig.com> accessed on the 18-8-2025, 8:56am
41. International Environmental Law Research Centre. *Gender, Conflict and Regional Security*. Maku mi Nwangiru ed. (2004). [Accessed 18-8-2025, 12:08pm] Available online: <file:///C:/Users/USER%20PC/Desktop/a0502.pdf>
42. Oloyede, O. *Monitoring Participation of Women in Politics in Nigeria*. National Bureau of Statistics. (2016).
43. Sulaiman, A. *Impact of Gender Gap on Women's Participation in Politics*. Special Issue on Economics, Management, Sociology, Communication, Psychology. (2025) [Accessed 27-7-2025]. Available online: <https://rsisinternational.org/journals/ijriss/articles/impact-of-gender-gap-on-women-s-participation-in-politics/DOI:https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRIS.2025.90600483>
44. Vlassoff, C. Gender Differences in Determinants and Consequences of Health and Illness. *J Health Popul Nutr* Mar;25(1):47-61. (2007), [ACCESSED 37-7-2025, 7:34PM] Available online: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3013263/>

45. MSM. Breaking Barriers: The Imperative for Gender Equality and Women Empowerment. Maastricht School of Management (2024) [Accessed 19-8-2025, 7:23pm] Available online: <https://www.msm.nl/news-events-and-blogs/blog/breaking-barriers-the-imperative-for-gender-equality-and-women-empowerment>
46. Carranza, E., Das, S. & Kotikula, A. Gender-Based Employment Segregation: Understanding Causes And Policy Interventions . International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank. (2023) [Accessed 28-7-2025, 4:54pm]. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/483621554129720460/pdf/Gender-Based-Employment-Segregation-Understanding-Causes-and-Policy-Interventions.pdf>
47. Africa Barometer. Africa women's political participation women's political participation, 2021: [Accessed 19-8-2025, 8:35pm]. Available online: <https://www.idea.int/sites/default/files/publications/womens-political-participation-africa-barometer2021.pdf>